

Effect of Thermal Degradation of Glass Fibre Sizing on Interfacial Adhesion

David Bryce, James Thomason, and Liu Yang

*22nd International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM23)
30th July – 4th August*

Background

- Global wind turbine waste > 43 million tonnes by 2050.
- Conventional waste disposal methods already banned in several European countries. Solutions needed urgently!
- Fibre properties reduced during composite recycling.
- Solutions need understanding of sizing decomposition

Overview

- *Characterisation relationship between elevated temperature processing and interfacial adhesion*
- **Methods:**
 - Glass fibres thermally conditioned at 200–500°C and reclaimed from wind blade using fluidised bed.
 - Sizing decomposition by thermogravimetric analysis.
 - Fibre surface analysis using FTIR.
 - Interfacial adhesion measured using microbond test.

Results:

Conclusions:

- Available at the poster session (Poster P091)

Effect of Thermal Degradation of Glass Fibre Sizing on Interfacial Adhesion

David Bryce, James Thomason, and Liu Yang
Advanced Composites Group, University of Strathclyde

Background

- Global wind turbine waste > 43 million tonnes by 2050.
- Conventional waste disposal methods already banned in several European countries. Solutions needed urgently!
- Fibre properties reduced during composite recycling.
- Solutions need understanding of sizing decomposition.
- Characterisation of relationship between elevated temperature processing and interfacial adhesion.

Methods

- Glass fibres thermally conditioned at 200–500°C.
- Fibres reclaimed from wind blade using fluidised bed.
- Sizing decomposition by thermogravimetric analysis.
- Fibre surface analysis using FTIR.
- Interfacial adhesion measured using microbond test.

Glass fibre sizing decomposition

- Sizing decomposition onset at 200°C
- Majority of mass loss in 200–400°C region.
- Further mass loss above 400°C attributable to coupling agent degradation.

TGA mass loss for glass fibres in air

Fibre surface analysis

- Hydroxyl group intensity indicative of lubricant removed by 250–300°C.
- Epoxy resin film former decreased with increasing treatment temperature and was removed completely following treatment at 300–350°C.
- Carbonyl growth indicates oxidised sizing material.

Glass fibre sizing spectral bands

FTIR spectra of thermally conditioned glass fibre surfaces

Interfacial adhesion

- IFSS stable up to treatment temperature of 300°C.
- Reduced adhesion onset at 350°C.
- Adhesion at 400–500°C comparable to unsized fibres.

Relationship between thermal conditioning temperature, sizing decomposition, and interfacial adhesion

Conclusions

- Sizing mass loss in the 200–400°C range attributable to degradation of an epoxy film former.
- Residue of degraded silane coupling agent at 350–500°C.
- Fluidised bed produced pristine glass fibre surface.
- Inverse relationship between IFSS and fibre treatment temperature concurrent with decomposition of sizing.
- Adhesion inhibited at higher treatment temperatures by the accumulation of weakly bound oxidised film former/sizing material on the glass fibre surface.

Future Work (ProGrESS 2022–25)

- £2 million three-year scheme to build pilot recycling facility and deliver a circular model for wind turbine blades.
- Continuous high-throughput reclamation of glass fibres from end-of-life composite materials.
- Reduce the manufacturing carbon footprint of GFRP materials by replacing virgin glass fibre with recycled glass fibre.
- Product development of composites incorporating recycled materials.
- Developing a sustainable solution to support a circular economy for end-of-life GFRP material as a green alternative to the current landfilling approach.

Future Work (ProGrESS 2022–25)

- £2 million three-year scheme to build pilot recycling facility and deliver a circular model for wind turbine blades.
- Continuous high-throughput reclamation of glass fibres from end-of-life composite materials
- Product development of composites incorporating recycled materials.
- Developing a sustainable solution to support a circular economy for end-of-life GFRP material as a green alternative to the current landfilling approach.

